

EFFECT OF BAITS TYPE ON FISH CONGREGATION AND CATCH EFFICIENCY OF CASTNET IN LAKE KAINJI, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The effect of baits, rice bran (*Oryza sativa* L.) and corn bran (*Zea mays* L.) on fish aggregation and catch efficiency of castnet in Lake Kainji was conducted. 25.4mm stretched mesh size multifilament (PA) nylon net was used for the construction of castnet. The experiment was Complete Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications for nineteen consecutive fishing days. Three treatments were employed; castnetting after baiting with rice bran, with corn-bran, and castnetting without bait (control). Thirteen fish species were caught from eight families. The number of fish caught was 336, of which 48.5 and 27.1% were castnetting with corn bran and without bait while castnetting with rice bran recorded the least (24.4%). The biomass of fish caught was 4627.7g (4.6kg) of which the highest percentages 51.4 and 28.6% followed same trend as that of number of fish caught. Comparison of the overall number and biomass of fish capture indicated that *Tilapia zilli* ranked highest, next by *Citharinus citharus* and *Hydrocynus forskalii*. Recommendations have been made for areas of further studies in these aspects.

INTRODUCTION

Castnet fishing is regarded as a traditional method of catching fish that has been used since antiquity. The most widely used artisanal fishing gears in Nigerian freshwater and brackish water as well as coastal waters, are gillnets and castnets (FAO, 1969). Castnet are conical falling nets with lead (Pb) weights attached at regular intervals along the perimeter of the cone (Udolisa and Solarin, 1979). It is an active fishing gear; that is it catches fish instantly.

Hayes *et al.* (1996) reported that a light or bait is often used to attract the target fish into an area within the castnet's range. Fishing baits lures and attraction devices, are often incorporated into some fishing gears in order to improve their efficiency such fishing gears include handlines, longlines, trolling and traps etc (Ahmed *et al.*, 2005). Baits may include rotten meat, dead or live fish, palm nuts or corn bran depending on the feeding and behavioral characteristics of the target fish species.

The castnet fishery is probably the next most damaging fishing method to juvenile fish after beach seines (du Feu and Abiodun, 1999). It caught 34% of the total tilapines, 24% *Citharinus* and 19% of all *Labeo*, at a mean size upto 50% less than gillnets in the case of *Citharinus*. This study therefore intends to assess the effects of two baits rice bran (*Oryza sativa* L.) and corn bran (*Zea mays* L.) and, without baits on the efficiency of castnet in Lake Kainji.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in the lower basin of Lake Kainji about 6.5 km away from the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, New Bussa, Niger State, between July and August, 2008. The description of study area is adequately made in Ahmed *et al.*, (2006).

The castnet construction was followed by the same method that was used by Udolisa *et al.* (1994) and Udolisa and Solarin (1979). Two types of baits were used corn bran and rice bran, and castnetting without bait was used as control. A net was cast, a waiting period of five minutes was observed to allow the weight to settle to the bottom of the sampling areas. The net was pulled with both hands to retrieve it. The experiment was Complete Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications for nineteen consecutive fishing days. The fish caught were packed in separate labelled container for each treatment.

The data were collected on species, number, length (cm) using metric ruler and weight (g) using Ohaus compact scale model CS200 of 200g capacity for each fish caught and recorded according to respective treatments. The fish species were identified following the description of Olaosebikan and Raji (2004).

Simple statistical tool was employed (mean and percentage) (SPSS, 1999). Species diversity index (SDI) was computed following Ahmed *et al.*, (2006) modified method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Types of Fish species Caught by Castnet using different baits in Lake Kainji.

The types of fish species captured comprise thirteen species belonging to eight fish families as shown in Table 1. The fish species diversity index showed that castnetting with corn bran had the highest value of 0.92, while castnetting without bait recorded 0.77 and with rice bran 0.69. Cichlidae family was represented by five species, Characidae with two species and the rest were represented by only one species each. Baits, lures or attraction devices are often incorporated into some fishing gears in order to improve their efficiency (Ahmed *et al.* 2005). Fish species that are dispersed over a wide range area can be congregated or concentrated into a smaller area where an appropriate fishing gear can be operated to get them. Congregation of fish before harvest had been reported by many authors using luring methods that are economically and environmentally friendly (Udolisa and Solarin, 1979; Solarin and Kusemiju, 2003). The fish species caught are from eight families, this shows that castnet is an efficient fishing gear for encountering fish species of diverse feeding and behavioral characteristics.

Number and percentages of fish Caught by castnet using different baits type in Lake Kainji.

Table 1 contains the number and percentages of fish caught with respect to the different treatments (baits). The total number of fish caught was 336, of which 48.5 and 27.1% were caught in castnetting with corn bran and castnetting without bait (control) respectively, while the least number (24.4%) was recorded in castnetting with rice bran. The findings in the present study show low catchability compared to that of Udolisa and Solarin (1979) at Ikorodu beach in the Lagos Lagoon, *Tilapia spp* are caught in large number about 5-10kg by spreading gari (Processed Cassava-*Manihot utilisina*) on marked spots and castnets are thrown over the area. The reason for the low catch in the study area has already been reported by Seisay and du Feu (1997) who observed a reduction in mean sizes in fish species and changes in species compositions due to both requirement and ecosystem over-fishing.

Comparison of the overall number of fish caught shows that *T. zilli* contributed the highest percentage, being 29.5% next by *C. citharus* 15.5%. Moreover, the dominant fish in the catches of castnet with corn bran was *T. zilli* that contributed 31.9%. In castnetting without bait *C. citharus* accounted for 38.5% while in fish entice with rice bran *T. zilli* accounted for 36.6% ranked next to this species was *H. forskalii*.

Table 1: Types, number and percentages of various fish species caught by Castnet during different baits type in Lake Kainji.

Family	Species	BAITS						Overall catch	
		Corn bran		Rice bran		Without bait		Total	Per-centage
		Number	Per-centage	Number	Per-centage	Number	Per-centage		
Characidae	<i>H. forskalii</i>	20	12.3	17	20.7	15	16.5	52	15.5
	<i>Alestes baremoze</i>	1	0.6	3	3.7	4	4.4	8	2.4
	<i>H. bimaculatus</i>	4	2.5	2	2.4	1	1.1	7	2.1
Cichlidae	<i>H. fasciatus</i>	13	7.9	8	9.8	6	6.6	27	8.0
	<i>Sarotherodon galilaeus</i>	7	4.3	5	6.1	1	1.1	13	3.9
	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	14	8.6	9	11.0	10	10.9	33	9.8
	<i>T. zilli</i>	52	31.9	30	36.6	17	18.7	99	29.5
	<i>C. citharus</i>	17	10.4	-	-	35	38.5	52	15.5
Claroteidae	<i>C. nigrodigitatus</i>	19	11.7	7	8.5	1	1.1	27	8.0
Cyprinidae	<i>Labeo coubie</i>	3	1.8	-	-	1	1.1	4	1.2
Distichodontidae	<i>Distichodus rostratus</i>	-	-	1	1.2	-	-	1	0.3
	<i>S. membranaceus</i>	6	3.7	-	-	-	-	6	1.8
Mormyridae	<i>M. budgeti</i>	7	4.3	-	-	-	-	7	2.1
Total number of fish caught		163	100	82	100	91	100	336	100
Relative Percentage		48.5		24.4		27.1			
Total species caught		12		9		10			
Species Diversity Index (SDI).		0.92		0.69		0.77			

Biomass and Percentages of fish species caught by castnet using different baits in the Lake Kainji.

The biomass of fish caught by castnetting using different baits are shown in Table 2. The total weight was 4627.7g (4.6kg) of which the greatest proportion 51.4 and 28.6% was captured in castnet baited with corn bran and without bait (control) while castnetting with rice bran recorded the least (20%). *T. zilli*, *C. citharus*, and *H. forskalii* contributed 25.4, 21.3 and 14.2 percents of the overall weight of fish caught. Comparison of the overall weight of the fish caught shows that fish entice with Corn bran *T. zilli* recorded for 29.3%, followed by *C. citharus* (15.6%). In castnetting with rice bran *T. zilli* accounted for 30.7% followed by *H. forskalii* while castnetting without bait (control) *C. citharus* contributed 46.4%.

Table 2: Biomass and percentages of various fish species caught by Castnet using different baits type in Lake Kainji.

Species	BAITS						Overall catch	
	Corn bran		Rice bran		Without bait		Total Weight (g)	Percentage
	Weight (g)	Percentage	Weight (g)	Percentage	Weight (g)	Percentage		
<i>H. forskalii</i>	224.0	9.4	182.2	19.6	253.2	19.1	659.5	14.2
<i>Alestes baremoze</i>	25.1	1.1	58.9	6.4	46.8	3.5	130.8	2.8
<i>H. bimaculatus</i>	30	1.3	22.7	2.4	8.5	0.6	61.2	1.3
<i>H. fasciatus</i>	123.2	5.2	130.7	14.1	61	4.6	314.9	6.8
<i>Sarotherodon galilaeus</i>	89.1	3.7	46.8	5.0	32.5	2.5	168.9	3.6
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	223.2	9.4	97.2	10.5	98.7	7.4	418.9	9.1
<i>T. zilli.</i>	696.1	29.3	285	30.7	195.6	14.8	1176.8	25.4
<i>C. citharus</i>	371.6	16.6	-	-	614.6	46.4	986.2	21.3
<i>C. nigrodigitatus</i>	310.8	13.1	89.4	9.6	8.3	0.6	408.5	8.8
<i>Labeo coubie</i>	20.5	0.9	-	-	4.7	0.4	25.2	0.5
<i>Distichodus rostratus</i>	-	-	14.5	1.6	-	-	14.5	0.3
<i>S. membranaceus</i>	143.3	6.0	-	-	-	-	143.3	3.1
<i>M. budgeti</i>	119.6	5.0	-	-	-	-	119.6	2.6
Total weight of fish caught	2376.5	100	927.4	100	1323.8	100	4627.7	100
Relative percentage	51.4		20.0		28.6			

CONCLUSION

At the end of this investigation the species caught was generally low, this might be due to overexploitation of the fisheries resources in the lake as a result of influx of fishermen and the use of undersized mesh. Though castnetting with corn bran recorded the highest number and weight of fish caught followed by castnetting without bait. It is therefore recommended for further study to be conducted in the lake using corn bran with other animal sources for inductive luring method,

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, Y.B., A.B. Adimula and E.F. Agbontaen (2005). Study on the effects of three fishing baits on the catch composition of Malian traps in Lake Kainji. In: P.A. Araoye (ed) *Processings of the 19th Annual Conference of the Fisheries Society of Nigeria, Ilorin, 29th November, - 3rd December 2004pp 557-562.*
- Ahmed, Y.B; J.K. Ipinjolu and W.A. Hasssan (2006). Catch composition of gillnets and baited longilines in the southern basin of Lake Kainji , Nigeria. In: Ansa, E.J. *et al.* (eds) *Processings of the 20th Annual National Conference of the Fisheries Society of Nigeria (FISON), Port-Harcourt, 14th – 18th November, 2005. Pp 350-360.*
- du Feu, T.A. and J.A. Abiodun (1999). Fisheries Statistics of Kainji Lake, Northern Nigeria, November 1994 – December, 1998. *Nigeria – German Kainji Lake Fisheries Promotion Project Technical Report Series 15.* 128p.

- FAO (1969). *Fisheries survey in the Western and Mid-western region of Nigeria*. United Nations Development Programme. FAO Rome.
- Hayes, D.B., C.P. Ferreri and W.W. Taylor (1996). Active fish Capture methods. In: B.R. Murphy and D.W. Willis (eds.) *Fisheries Techniques*, 2nd Edition, American Fisheries Society, Bethesda Maryland. Pp193-220.
- Olaosebikan, B.D. and A. Raji (2004). *Field Guide to Nigerian Freshwater Fishes*. 2nd edition published by FCFPT, New Bussa, Unilorin Press, Ilorin-Nigeria. 111p
- Seisay, M.D.B. and T.A. du Feu (1997). The effect of long term exploitation by gillnet fishery on the multi-species fish stocks in Kainji Lake. *NGKLFPP Technical report Series* 11.58p.
- Solarin, B.B. and K. Kusemiju (2003). Fish Shelter as Fisheries Enhancement Techniques in Lagos Lagoon, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Fisheries* 1(1): 57-61.
- SPSS (1999). Statistical Package for the Social Sciences SPSS for Windows release 10.0.1 Standard Version.
- Udolisa, R.E.K. and B.B. Solarin (1979). Design Characteristics of Castnets and Gillnets in Lagos Lagos Nigeria. *NIOMR Occasional Paper Number 31*, 24p.
- Udolisa, R.E.K; B.B. Solarin, P. Lebo and E.E. Ambrose (1994). *A catalogue of small scale fishing gear in Nigeria* . RAFR/014/F1/94/02:142P.

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